

KNOWLEDGE EXCHANGE SURVEY

MISTRAL INNOVATIVE TRAINING NETWORK 2022

Analysis by Ben McAteer and Geraint Ellis*

*Correspondence address: g.ellis@qub.ac.uk

With contributions from:

Zoé Chateau, Elizabeth Côté, Jakob Knauf, Alex Miller, Jean-Pierre Roux, Nina Schneider, Mariangela Vespa, and Ross Wallace

<https://mistral-itn.eu/>

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie actions grant agreement MISTRAL No 813837

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie actions grant agreement MISTRAL No 813837

MISTRAL-ITN Knowledge Exchange Survey

MISTRAL Knowledge Exchange Survey

Contents

1. Introduction	2
2. Researcher background and experience	3
3. Perceptions of research use and impact	9
4. Knowledge exchange in practice and understanding research users	12
4.1 Understanding the needs of research users and how to respond to them	12
4.2 Processes and techniques of creating research impact	16
4.3 Use of online platforms to share and access academic material	19
4.4 Collaboration with research users	21
5. Self-reflection on knowledge exchange going forward	24
6. Key findings and conclusions	29
Appendix: Search criteria for identifying participants in the MISTRAL Knowledge exchange Survey	31

List of Figures

Figure 1: Cycle of Knowledge Exchange	2
Figure 2: Gender of Participants	3
Figure 3: Age of participants	3
Figure 4: Geographic location of participants	4
Figure 5: Nature of research institution	5
Figure 6: Orientation of research institution	5
Figure 7: Participants role at their institution	6
Figure 8: Participant research experience	6
Figure 9: Participants' areas of research	7
Figure 10: Geographic scale of participants research	8
Figure 11: Participant research in policy or practitioner environments	8

MISTRAL-ITN Knowledge Exchange Survey

1. Introduction

This report presents an analysis of a MISTRAL knowledge exchange survey completed by 892 researchers working on social science aspects of sustainability from around the world in 2020 (See Appendix for search criteria). This had the aim of generating insights into their approach to research communication and knowledge exchange. The online survey posed a range of questions regarding researcher background, perceptions of research use and impact, researchers' understanding of users, and self-reflection on how knowledge exchange processes can be improved moving forward. The survey was based on the 'Exchange' model of knowledge exchange shown in Figure 1, which envisages this to be a continual process of action, implementation, and reflection. This survey is aimed at increasing the level of reflection in this process.

Figure 1: Cycle of Knowledge Exchange

A diverse array of responses were received, indicating both trends amongst groups of researchers and differing perspectives regarding certain aspects of how knowledge can most effectively be exchanged and create impact. This report presents the results of the analysed survey responses. The findings are broken down into 4 separate sections. To begin, a review of the institutional background of researchers, as well as an assessment of their research experience, is presented in section 2. This is followed by an evaluation of how researchers perceive the use and impact of their produced knowledge in section 3. Section 4 presents an in-depth assessment of the responses of researchers to questions regarding knowledge exchange in practice and how they understand the needs and requirements of research users. To conclude the findings of this report, section 5 illustrates how researchers self-reflect on the knowledge exchange process and what their perceptions are of the major opportunities and barriers moving forward. This report presents interesting and important insight on the experiences and opinions of research producers. It highlights the key limitations and concerns that researchers have and contains information that can be useful in informing knowledge exchange procedures and impact pathways in the future. A conclusion is presented in section 6 of this report, where the major findings are recapped, along with some final remarks.

2. Researcher background and experience

This section presents a descriptive analysis of the participating researchers. Amongst all survey participants a greater percentage of researchers are male (63.4%) than female (35.5%). This is illustrated in *Fig. 2*. A further 1.0% of participants preferred not to state their gender, whilst 0.1% identified as non-binary. In regard to the age range of researchers, the most predominant category was 35-44 years (31.1%). Similar proportions of participants are aged between 25-34 (18%) and 45-54 (18.7%). A significantly smaller percentage of researchers are under the age of 25 (0.2%), with a further 8% between 55-64 and 4.6% above the age of 65. This information is reflected in *Fig 3*.

Figure 2: Gender of Participants

Figure 3: Age of participants

Figure 4 illustrates the geographical spread of researchers. The countries that most researchers live in include the United States of America (9.6%), the United Kingdom (5.5%), Germany (4.4%), Spain (3.3%) and China (3.2%). More broadly, other European nations, including Denmark (1.1%), Finland (1.1%), France (0.9%),

MISTRAL-ITN Knowledge Exchange Survey

Ireland (1%), Italy (2.7%), the Netherlands (1.7%), Portugal (1.2%), Sweden (2%) and Switzerland (2.2%), are well represented amongst researchers. Smaller proportions of participants are located in South American countries, with Brazil (1.9%) the most common nation, and in parts of Asia, the Middle East and Africa. A total of 2% of participants are located in Australia, 1.8% in India and a further 1.4% in Mexico. These findings represent an insightful overview of where researchers are most commonly residing throughout the world. There are clear trends of high representation within Europe, as well as in China and North America. Beyond this, however, there are much lower levels of spread amongst countries. Largely, this is due to the location of research institutions and universities. There are much greater quantities of highly respected and well-resourced research institutions and universities in the western world, for instance.

Figure 4: Geographic location of participants

In relation to the nature of participants' research institutions and universities, as illustrated in *Figure 5*, the vast majority were 'predominantly publicly funded' (66.1%). Significantly smaller proportions of participants are based in institutes or universities that are 'predominantly privately funded' (5.7%) or in 'non-profit/charity/NGO' organisations (4.4%). Furthermore, *Figure 6* shows how almost half of all participants (48.7%) are based within institutions or universities that have an equal focus on teaching and research. Slightly under one quarter of participants (21%) work within institutions or universities that are primarily teaching oriented, with only 9.8% in teaching oriented settings.

MISTRAL-ITN Knowledge Exchange Survey

Figure 5: Nature of research institution

Figure 6: Orientation of research institution

Almost three quarters of participants (71.6%) work full-time in their research positions, with a further 10.4% in part-time positions and the remaining participants preferring not to say. In regard to the permanence of researchers in their current positions, 62.4% of participants state that they have a permanent contract. This means that a significantly high proportion of over a third of participants (37.6%) do not have a permanent contract. These findings further reflect the concerns of researchers across the world regarding the precarity and short-term nature of their employment, which is likely to have an impact on the relationships they can build with non-academic partners. As the following sections of this report will reveal, these factors are having a detrimental effect upon the potential of researchers to maximise their output. Consequently, this can hinder the potential research impact of researchers. In relation to the role of researchers, as shown in *Figure 7*, the vast majority of participants state that they are 'staff working on research with teaching responsibilities' (62.4%). Around one quarter of participants (25.7%) work solely on research responsibilities and a much smaller proportion focus exclusively on teaching responsibilities (1.2%). Other roles include consultant positions,

MISTRAL-ITN Knowledge Exchange Survey

directors of research or education, Doctoral students, those holding Professor Emeritus positions, and research staff working mainly in administrative roles.

Figure 7: Participants role at their institution

Research experience is a vital component for researchers, particularly in relation to their ability to transfer to new projects or to gain a permanent contract. Illustrated in *Figure 8*, over half of all participants (53.5%) state that they have 'more than 10 years' of research experience. A further 19.8% have 7-10 years of experience, with around one quarter (22.8%) of participants currently having 3-6 years of experience. Only 3.8% of researchers have less than 2 years' experience, demonstrating the relatively limited array of early career researchers in research institutions and universities. In relation to the broad area(s) of research that participants work within, *Figure 9* illustrates how over one half (53.3%) conduct social science research. Over one third of participants (35.6%) work in the area of engineering and physical sciences. Lesser amounts of participants conduct research within the fields of biotechnology and biological sciences (2.6%) or arts and humanities (5.7%). Other fields of research that are mentioned by participants include economics and finance, business management, and architecture.

Figure 8: Participant research experience

MISTRAL-ITN Knowledge Exchange Survey

Figure 9: Participants' areas of research

A small finding of note regards the location of where participants conduct their research, as highlighted in *Figure 10*. Over two thirds of participants (69.4%) carry out research where their organisation is located. A further 30.6% of participants carry out their research in an international capacity. In the comments of participants, it is revealed that partnerships between research institutions and universities in different countries is a key requirement for conducting research internationally. Particularly for researchers based within Europe, a number of participants note that they often conduct research in a comparative manner across multiple nations. For instance, participants state that they carry out their research in "a number of nations in the EU (Spain, Netherlands, UK, Ireland, France)" (12130113345¹), and how they are "closely collaborating with EU institutions (Greece, Sweden, Austria, Finland, Cyprus)" (12206675411). Beyond this, researchers note how being aligned with global organisations, such as the United Nations, can mean that they continuously work in the international realm. As one respondent noted, "I most recently have been researching in partnership with the United Nations regarding their climate change negotiations" (12129795090). Other researchers discuss how their research is internationally focused on specific regions or areas of the globe that they interested in. This includes participants that conduct research "across the Global South" (12152320074), "within the North Sea Region: Netherlands, Germany, Belgium, Denmark, Norway, Sweden, Scotland" (12215730332), and across "sub-Saharan Africa" (12206956780).

¹ The numbers reflect the anonymous participant number used in the research

MISTRAL-ITN Knowledge Exchange Survey

Figure 10: Geographic scale of participants research

Figure 11: Participant research in policy or practitioner environments

A final finding within this section relates to the experience of researchers within a policy or professional (practitioner) environment, as illustrated in *Figure 11*. Whilst one quarter of participants (27%) state that they have no experience of working within these realms, a significant proportion of researchers revealed that they have varying degrees of experience as a consultant while in academia (25.9%), for short-term periods whilst between jobs (17.2%), and in full-time positions (26.2%). In open responses, researchers noted how they had worked “in a consultant role to government agencies developing energy-related policies” (12138340880) and “in applied, policy-oriented research” (12131164927). The significance of this finding relates to the potential knowledge and insight that researchers have developed in consultancy and practitioner roles. Key learning lessons of how knowledge is most commonly used in professional and practitioner settings could help to inform the research exchange strategies that are followed by researchers. The degree to which this possibility is realised by researchers is revealed throughout the forthcoming sections, with varying amounts of researchers discussing how their experience of consulting and practitioner roles have influenced how they seek to exchange and instigate impact through their research.

3. Perceptions of research use and impact

This section reflects the general perceptions of research producers regarding the use and impact of their research. The findings in this theme are sourced from two statements that questioned how participants believe academia should seek to instigate impact. The first statement asked if researchers could have the greatest impact by striving to be advocates of particular issues and to actively promote the change based on the evidence they have, or by striving to be an objective honest broker of knowledge on a specific issue. The responses were relatively split between the two options, as illustrated in *Figure 3.1*. A total of 49.5% aligned with the perception that researchers should strive to be advocates of particular issues, while a further 36.9% stated that they believe research can have the greatest impact if researchers act as honest brokers of knowledge. Additionally, 13.6% of participants suggested alternative options.

Figure 12: Participants' attitude to research impact

A large number of participants were keen to highlight that "impact requires academics working in both capacities" (12171394517) and that "a delicate balance of the above two options must be found for research to be effective" (12154358654). Indeed, research requires "a combination of the two - honest brokering but, given all knowledge is political, it's important to adhere to values, transparently" (12129420278). One respondent echoed this perception by stating that "we need to be both 'objective' and an advocate at some level - mainly in regard to knowledge mobilization (ensuring findings get to all the relevant audiences)" (12130986419). These perceptions highlight how researchers must be flexible and capable of acting as both advocates for specific issues and objective brokers of knowledge. Furthermore, some participants were keen to highlight how the answer to a question such as this relies upon context. For instance, one respondent stated that "research impact is hugely dependent on the particular knowledge and/or issues in the frame" (12133725387). Therefore, to instigate the desired impact, participants suggest that researchers must calculate the appropriate approach to follow when it comes to producing and exchanging knowledge. Beyond this, other participants put forward practical ideas of how research can most effectively instigate impact. One respondent suggested that researchers can have the greatest impact "by generating data bases and analyses relevant for both academia and policy makers; by empowering actors in specific fields to find innovative solutions" (12238761366). Additional perceptions included those that suggested how researchers must "have the opportunity to transfer their own

MISTRAL-ITN Knowledge Exchange Survey

technology to the society creating spin-offs and/or start-ups" (12125624660). Others presented more cautious interpretations, suggested that they *"trust the second option more but do not know if it is the one that has the greatest impact"* (12152784047), reflecting the need for researchers to self-reflect upon their work and to gauge the tactics required to make an impact within their field of research. Furthering this point, a respondent asserted that *"academics should be trained better to communicate through popular social media channels. Communication via these channels need to recognised (sic) for career progression or else academics will stick to traditional academic publishing which has minimal impact in broader society"* (12206759898). Critically reviewing the context and conditions of one's research, and the potential pathways to impact that exist, appear central to the thinking of researchers.

The second finding provided in this section reveals the perceptions of participants regarding how researchers should engage with potential users. Asked whether an ad hoc approach should be followed where engagement with external organisations is carried out on an issue by issue basis, or whether long-term relationships should be developed with potential users, participants were split. Almost equal numbers of researchers aligned with the former statement (36.7%) as with the latter (38.9%). This, once more, reflected the importance of context with the realm of research. Participants spoke of how *"a combination of long-term relationships and issues-based engagement is needed"* (12207008844) and how *"I do both of the above. I consider myself an action researcher, and thus I work on both platforms"* (12128568611). These perceptions were furthered by participants who asserted that *"in practice, more of the latter, but I desire to achieve the former"* (12206841185) and that *"sometimes you may not have to keep or maintain some relationships. At other times, it will be absolutely essential"* (12223236454).

Figure 13: Participant engagement with potential users of research

Further context-dependent issues were raised by participants, including the fact that *"it depends on the organisation, their resources, time, interest, etc."* (12171394517). Although researchers may have desires to develop long-term relationships with potential users, they must be aware that not all users will have the capacity to establish such relationships. In such scenarios, it becomes more effective to engage on a case by case basis. These concerns are furthered by participants who note organisational and political restrictions that can hinder their engagement approaches. For example, one researcher stated that *"Brazilian relationships between university and stakeholders are still incipient"* (12164215852), whilst another asserted that *"although I would like to foster long-term relationships with those organization that are best placed to use my research, there*

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie actions grant agreement MISTRAL No 813837

MISTRAL-ITN Knowledge Exchange Survey

are no such relationships in Nigeria" (12129957593). Financial restrictions are also noted by researchers, with one arguing that *"I would like to foster long term relationships, but the way projects are usually funded, engagement is only within specific timescales, often without further communication (at least in official capacities)"* (12143909512). The issue of time-bound funding for research is reflected by many researchers throughout this report and it is revealed as a key hindrance to attempts of creating long-term relationships between research producers and users. In addition to this, some researchers state that they *"don't engage with external users"* (12134605850) and that they *"lack the experience to disseminate and exchange constructively on my research"* (12206584266). This highlights how training and experience building in the realm of knowledge exchange is vital to successful exchange processes. These findings highlight a broad range of perceptions regarding the most effective and efficient ways of developing impact through research. Whilst there are divergent opinions amongst researchers, there are also clear trends that suggest how engagement strategies must be considered within the context of one's research field.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie actions grant agreement MISTRAL No 813837

MISTRAL-ITN Knowledge Exchange Survey

4. Knowledge exchange in practice and understanding research users

This section discusses how researchers consider the needs of potential research users and the avenues through which they attempt to transfer knowledge. These are key themes in relation to knowledge exchange and research impact. The section highlights how researchers attempt to channel the knowledge that they create to the area and users that they perceive offer the opportunity of generating impact. This insight is important, specifically as it illustrates the key opportunities and barriers to exchanging knowledge, from research producer's perspective. The challenges of using research to inform policy and practice are well documented, with an evidence base for interventions or programmes traditionally contested. In response to these challenges, an abundance of models and frameworks have been developed that try to define the knowledge exchange process (how research evidence can be used, in combination with other types of knowledge, to change policy and practice). The findings presented in this theme highlight how some researchers venturing into the field of knowledge exchange can be uncertain by the options available. However, there is a strong cohort of researchers that have, through practice and experience, identified successful pathways to exchanging knowledge with a range of audiences.

This section has been divided into four sub-sections, the first of which reviews how researchers understand the needs of research users (section 4.1). This includes the responses of researchers to question regarding their experience of knowledge exchange techniques, communicating research to non-academic audiences, and the level of communication that researchers have with key external stakeholders. The second sub-theme explores the processes and techniques of creating research impact (section 4.2). This includes assessments of the degree to which researchers prioritize studies that have the potential to produce 'actionable-messages' or can directly impact those working in policy and practice. Other aspects of this sub-theme involve analysing the degree to which researchers enable users to participate in the design and process of their research. A third sub-theme presents insight on the manner in which researchers use online platforms to share and access academic material (section 4.3). This involves information on the ability to publish Open Access and their use of social media to share research. A final sub-theme looks at how researchers work with research users (section 4.4). Here, information is revealed regarding the frequency in which researchers work with potential research users on training and capacity building for acquiring, assessing, adapting, and applying academic research.

4.1 Understanding the needs of research users and how to respond to them

A majority of researchers consider that that they have a 'good understanding' of the research needs of potential users. Over half of the participants, 56%, agree with the statement (*Figure 14*). As one respondent noted, "*engaging with stakeholders in order to understand the issues they are facing and coming back to them communicating our findings to let the research have a broad impact is an important core value of my research unit within the university*" (12213086277). There is an appreciation amongst a large proportion of researchers that developing a close relationship with potential users is crucial to the efficient and effective exchange of knowledge. Thus, identifying the needs of research users, and aligning their research with these, is a key theme for many knowledge producers. This is reflected by the fact that only 8% of researchers disagree or strongly disagree with the statement that they have a good understanding of such needs. However, participants note that the task of identifying the needs of potential research users and of exchanging knowledge with them is not something that they regularly receive support for. One researcher explained that: "*I have learned the best ways to engage with stakeholders despite the lack of support, guidance or training offered by most universities. Research is valued once the outputs are achieved (funding, publications) but little to help researchers get there*" (12211264549). This suggests that, although researchers are well versed in what research users require, it is the responsibility of researchers themselves to initiate knowledge exchange processes.

MISTRAL-ITN Knowledge Exchange Survey

Figure 14: Participants' understanding of the needs of potential research users

A further theme that emerged from the data relates to the experience of researchers to effectively communicate their research findings to non-academics. *Figure 15* highlights how a high majority of researchers agree (59%) or strongly agree (23%) with this statement. This demonstrates how researchers acknowledge that it is not solely through academic channels that knowledge can be exchanged. Rather, identifying connections with non-academics is crucial to enhancing the potential impact of research. It is also revealed that to reach non-academic audiences, different approaches to knowledge exchange are required, with less focus of publications and more on a range of digestible sources of information. As one respondent noted, this can offer a greater potential for research impact to be developed:

"I find that engaging with non-academic audiences (public and government) is more productive than journal publications. Educating the public is more important than publishing papers that a core group of fellow academics read. Granted, there are world-class researchers who should publish in major journals, for me, getting the public to understand the relationship between energy and the environment is key if we are to address important issues like climate change" (12150716607).

There is an evident understanding that engaging with non-academic audiences is vital to developing the public consciousness of important research topics, including climate issues. However, the same respondent asserted that committing resources and time to engaging with non-academics *"has affected my ability to attract research funds"* (12150716607). This hints that engagement with non-academic audiences is framed, in research funding circles, as a task that falls beyond the necessary activities of research producers. Not only are attempts to establish knowledge exchange links with non-academics interpreted as additional to the required work of researchers, they are perceived by one respondent as being detrimental to obtaining research funding. However, such concerns are not shared by all researchers. As one respondent stated, *"in my country there are specific grants for applied research projects, where involvement of non-academic stakeholders is obligatory"* (12125043434). This suggests that contrasting interpretations of the importance of exchanging knowledge with non-academics exist within different countries, resulting in varying levels of support for this form of

MISTRAL-ITN Knowledge Exchange Survey

engagement. This was further evidence by a respondent who suggested that *"the difference is enormous between different countries. My negative answers refer to my new institute, which is in my home country. I worked in the UK where everything was so much stronger in the respect of being expected to engage with different stakeholders"* (12163905627).

Figure 15: Participants' experience of communicating with non-academic audiences

When responding to questions regarding the degree to which researchers feel confident that their research strengths are understood by external stakeholders (Figure 16), and the frequency of engagement between research producers and users (Figure 17), the results reveal greater divergence amongst researchers. Indeed, a high number of participants (38%) suggest that they neither agree nor disagree when asked whether researchers users are aware of their strengths. Just over one third of researchers either agree (36%) or strongly agree (7%) when responding to the statement. This suggests that the relationship between research producers and users can significantly vary, meaning that the degree to which users are familiar with the work, skills and potential output of research producers can vary. As one participant suggests, this can be the result of changing audiences. *"Public administrations (potential research users) have very complex structures and timeline and very volatile plans (also depending on the people in charge that are rapidly changing) which makes the implementation of research results not always feasible in the best way"* (12206676870). This ever-changing environment appears to be a factor that can limit the ability of research producers to establish strong lines of connection and communication with potential audiences. This is also reflected the frequency of engagement between research producers and potential users. Figure 5.4 illustrates how almost one quarter of participants (23%) feel that they do not regularly meet research users, hindering their capacity to extend cooperation and to develop mutual capacities. A further 28% of participants neither agree nor disagree with this statement. There is, however, one third of participants who agree (35%) or strongly agree (10%) with the statement. This reveals a large contrast within the field of researchers, with some frequently extending relationships between themselves and research users, and others finding it difficult to do so. The key to establishing cooperation between producers and users, it appears, is the creation of consistent dialogue between actors. Through such partnerships, research producers can learn how to align with the intentions of users, and trust and working relationships can develop accordingly. However, this is no easy task, with one respondent arguing that *"it is very difficult to establish lines of good communication"* (12129051267). This is furthered by a research producer

MISTRAL-ITN Knowledge Exchange Survey

who states that there is “*much work to be done in this area. A virtual workshop with stakeholders and a report, do not seem sufficient*” (12130986419).

Figure 16: External stakeholders' understanding of research strengths

Figure 17: Regular meetings between researchers and external stakeholders

A further finding that emerged from this sub-theme relates to researchers' understanding of the role of non-academic channels of communication, such as social media (Twitter, LinkedIn), to engage with non-academic users of knowledge (Figure 18). A majority of researchers either agreed (36%) or strongly agreed (15%) with a

MISTRAL-ITN Knowledge Exchange Survey

statement that asked if they regularly utilise such channels. This is reflective of a shift amongst research producers to identify the most relevant and potentially impactful channels through which knowledge can be shared and exchanged. For instance, one respondent noted how they “*blog and engage in media, panels and podcasts*” (12130347919). Another stated that they “*communicate my research results by popular articles, media and addressing organisations (currently by Zoom)*” (12126080360). Using online channels to exchange research findings appears as an increasingly valuable way of engaging with new audiences, many of whom may be excluded from more professional or academic channels. Despite the growth of these channels, over one quarter of participants either disagreed (22%) or strongly disagreed (8%) with the statement. This suggests that there is research that remains exclusive to academic channels and, in the opinion of some participants, is the most effective means of creating research impact. As one producer noted, “*not all worthwhile research is designed to go directly to public users. Most of my research is directed at a scholarly audience, so little of this applies to my own situation*” (12125949355).

Figure 18: Participants use of non-academic channels of communication

4.2 Processes and techniques of creating research impact

When knowledge is exchanged, it has the capacity to create impact upon a wide array of practices and processes. Survey findings indicate that the potential of research to impact upon evidence-based decision making is a consideration of particular note for many researchers (Figure 4.6). Over half of survey participants noted that they agree (38.3%) or strongly agree (22.8%) with the statement that generating research impact by contributing to evidence-bases is key to their thinking. Only 3.5% of participants disagreed with this statement, highlighting how interacting with evidence-based decisions making circles is a key factor that research producers take into consideration when designing research projects. As one researcher stated, “*research has to have an impact in solving the problems of my community and state, and not be something hypothetical. This means that I always try to contribute to the evidence bases that inform the thinking of decision makers*” (12129420278). Another respondent suggested that funding arrangements can push researchers to prioritize any potential engagement with decision makers. They noted that, “*I mainly get external funding from government agencies and therefore have to consider policy relevance*” (12125567012). Although exchanging

MISTRAL-ITN Knowledge Exchange Survey

research findings with decision makers is only one of many possible avenues through which research can create impact, it appears as a key consideration for a large proportion of researchers.

Figure 19: Research impact through evidence-based decision-making

An apparent barrier to creating research impact is the necessity for many research producers to, first and foremost, publish their work in peer reviewed journals. Over half of the survey participants either agree (29.2%) or strongly agree (26.6%) with the statement that they prioritize papers for journals above other forms of output (Figure 4.7). Clarifying this dominant perspective, one research noted that “peer reviewed outputs are important for the legitimacy of the research” (12129420278). A number of participants, whilst in agreement with the statement, demonstrated how they “have immense pressure to publish for me to progress in my academic career” (12128711996) and that their “university was more concerned with publishing than applications of the research results” (12208029294). A further respondent noted that, although they “do a lot of stakeholder engaged research ... being pre tenure means that I have to publish in peer reviewed journals” (12210815678). These findings suggest that many research producers are forced, either by institutional requirements or by career objectives, to focus on publishing their research in peer reviewed, academic journals. This can limit the capacity of researchers to explore alternative means of creating research impact and hinder their ability to exchange knowledge with a wider audience.

Figure 20: Participants prioritisation of peer reviewed journals

MISTRAL-ITN Knowledge Exchange Survey

When asked about the participation of stakeholders and potential research users in their research, participants showed divergence in their perspectives of how important, and feasible, it is (*Figure 21*). Responding to a statement that asked if research users are able to actively engage with the design and process of research, over one third of participants either agreed (29.9%) or strongly agreed (9.1%) that they ensure that participation is possible. However, a high proportion of participants neither agreed nor disagreed (21.8%) with the statement, with a further 10.1% in disagreement. The additional comments of participants reveal how participation in research can be a context-dependent issue. *"It depends on the project - some projects are more participatory than others"* (12130716577). Funding conditions and partnerships can also have an influence upon the degree to which research involves others, with one respondent stating that: *"as I work in a highly political area, all the policy and practice stakeholders I engage with appreciate the university conducting the project independently of all others"* (12129420278). This perspective is supported by another respondent, who asserts that their *"main research integrity mechanism is to avoid involvement by potential users in data gathering and analysis. Involvement at other stages can always be declared as an existing precondition or bias, but involvement in data gathering/analysis is much harder to manage"* (12128303078). Despite the potential value of enabling participation in the design and process of research, it is evident that there are barriers that researchers must overcome should they be able to ensure this. One respondent suggested that *"the best way to engage with stakeholders/users is to create a common project where there is funding for their participation - then you can get good results in making use of their knowledge and to disseminate results to them"* (12125508818).

Figure 21: Research users participation in research

Further comments from participants revealed that ethical and political reasons can hinder the involvement of stakeholders and users in the research process. One researcher stated that they *"think it is usually problematic to engage in knowledge exchange while undertaking data gathering. This should be done up front or afterwards, due to the potential for bias"* (12128677140). Moreover, one respondent noted how political conditions can make it difficult to conduct research and can hinder the capacity of research to inform policy. They reflected how *"the science and technology policy adopted by the current Brazilian government, a situation aggravated by the pandemic, has interrupted several research projects and hampered access to financial resources"* (12216113420). A further comment by a respondent illustrated the many barriers that researchers can face when attempting to contribute to evidence bases that can inform policy. Largely, this relates to the ability of policy makers to overpower researchers. The respondent stated that, *"policymakers and practitioners alike are usually looking for a justification for the decision they've already made ... trying to serve that need, however good the intentions, will end up distorting the research through either the framing of the research questions or the*

MISTRAL-ITN Knowledge Exchange Survey

phrasing of the findings" (12133725387). This highlights how policy makers can request specific types of knowledge that align with their agenda, an issue that can insert bias to the research process.

4.3 Use of online platforms to share and access academic material

The engagement of research producers with online platforms has become increasingly common in recent years. Researchers can share their own work on academic websites or via social media. This means that there is an ever-increasing amount of academic material available to access via online services, widening the potential audience that can view and learn from research outputs. It also enhances the potential for knowledge exchange amongst research producers and users. *Figure 22* illustrates the regularity of researchers uploading research material to their university or research institutions websites. It suggests that these websites are not the priority for researchers, with almost one third of all participants (30%) stating that they only 'sometimes' upload material there. Only half of this amount respond by saying that they 'always' (14.2%) use these services. Similar results are revealed in regard to the frequency of researchers uploading their academic output to online databases, such as Figshare or Academia.edu (*Figure 23*). Only 14.4% of participants 'always' upload to these databases, whilst 22.7% 'sometimes' do and a further 15.5% 'never'. This suggests that university websites and academic databases are rarely the priority location for researchers to upload their material. Perhaps, they represent additional options that can hold downloadable copies or access links to already published academic material. Participants note how they also utilise a range of other academic databases, including "Google Scholar, ORCID, RG, Web of Science Publons" (12126779769), which offers similar opportunities. Moreover, some researchers make use of their "own independent website" (12127967905), with a further respondent noting how they tend to upload their academic material to "the think tank we work closely with (Common Weal) and it's media arm (Source News)" (12125178383).

Figure 22: Participants' upload of research to university websites

MISTRAL-ITN Knowledge Exchange Survey

Figure 23: Regularity of upload of research to online sources

A key discussion point for participants regarded their ability, and tendency, to publish research material via open access. *Figure 24* illustrates the regularity of researchers to publish their academic papers in subscription and open access journals. Most notably, it is revealed that a higher proportion of participants 'always' publish in subscription journals (21.8%) than in open access journals (12.1%). Largely, this relates to difficulties and significant expenses that are encountered when attempting to publish in open access journals. Despite the benefits of having their academic papers accessible to a wider range of potential research users, participants state that this is outweighed by costs and other limitations. As one researcher noted, *"I don't usually publish in Open Access only journals, like the rubbishy MDPI ones, because they take a lot of poor quality work. But I do nearly always pay (extortionate) open access fees to traditional subscription journals (i.e. gold open access model). I wish I didn't have to, but I'm not going to throw my research away by putting it into a junk journal just because it's open access"* (12206546439). Other researchers state how institutional limitations can restrict their ability to publish with open access journals, as *"there is typically no budget in research programs to pay for the associated fees"* (12129123367). These barriers are recognised as significantly weakening the knowledge exchange capabilities of research producers, with one respondent arguing that *"research output has to be accessible to the policy makers and the common man, which is why open access, despite its cost, is crucial"* (12129890885). The survey findings also reveal how the accessibility of research producers to academic material is not always secured. One respondent stated how they *"don't have the deal with Elsevier, so [they have] limited access to new papers and no open access publications"* (12206966296). In total, survey participants note how open access, although desirable for both research producers and users, is an exceedingly expensive option that is simply not available to the majority of researchers. Institutional support appears necessary for this to change.

MISTRAL-ITN Knowledge Exchange Survey

Figure 24: Publishing in subscription vs open access journals

A range of alternative means of sharing and accessing research material online is suggested by multiple researchers. Many of these are utilised as a way of reaching a multitude of potential research users, something which is not consistently possible via more traditional online process of knowledge exchange. Alternative approaches include "free webinars that we organize" (12126768266) and "public electronic communication media (diffusion magazines, newsletters, radio interviews, podcasts, etc.)" (12224028664). Other comments reflect how researchers "publish on *The Conversation*, a web platform for academics to communicate research to general audiences. This is a very effective mechanism as many media channels use this platform as a source of information" (12129123367). Moreover, one respondent stated that they "always make stakeholder-relevant products available to university media relations personnel and work with them to identify most relevant highlights for press releases, which are picked up by news outlets in local communities and shared online" (12207718261). Finally, it is noted by several participants that uploading 'pre-print' versions of published papers is one option of getting around the restrictions of open access. This is complimented by ideas of producing several different types of formal and informal versions of research outputs whilst the research process remains in progress. As one respondent explained, "I put my work in progress on preprint servers, as well as the computational models that I develop. I also publish all the code and user guides free and open access on my own blog (hence direct to potential research users)" (12206546439).

4.4 Collaboration with research users

A final sub-theme that emerged from the survey responses regarded collaboration between researcher producers and users at the completion of the research process. This does not consider how researchers engaged with users in data collection, analysis or even project design phases. Instead, it reveals insight on how collaboration between these two actors takes place after a project has been completed. Figure 25 highlights how the vast majority of researchers either 'sometimes' (47%), 'often' (35%) or 'always' (11%) produce reports for non-academics at the end of research projects. These are not academic publications. Rather, they are documents that translate the research findings into more accessible, jargon-free discourse and are focused on emphasising to research users the value of the work. Only 7% of participants 'never' make use of such reports, highlighting how they have become a common output for researchers.

MISTRAL-ITN Knowledge Exchange Survey

Figure 25: Producing of reports for non-academic audiences on completion of projects

Moreover, the survey findings reveal how collaboration between producers and users can also involve training and capacity building. In particular, researchers responded positively to a statement that asked if they support research users in regard to acquiring, assessing, adapting, and applying academic research. *Figure 26* shows how almost half of the survey participants 'sometimes' conduct such collaborative sessions, while a further 28% 'often' do and 5% 'always' support the creation of training events. This is deemed as a forward-looking approach to helping potential research users understand how to utilise academic research in efficient and effective ways. Added to this, *Figure 4.14* illustrates how collaboration can include work with research users to improve their capacity to interpret the implications of academic research for policy and practice. Similarly high numbers of participants either 'sometimes' (48%) or 'sometimes' (29%) support such processes, with a further 6% 'always' doing so. These examples highlight how collaboration is not solely an important component of research production at the initial stages of projects, but also after completion.

Figure 26: Participants' capacity building with research users

MISTRAL-ITN Knowledge Exchange Survey

'Working with potential research users to interpret the implications of academic research for policy and practice and co-design communication materials'

Figure 27: Participants work with research users on the implications of their research

5. Self-reflection on knowledge exchange going forward

This section presents information on the manner in which researchers reflect on the opportunities and challenges of knowledge exchange going forward. Beginning with a reflection on their institutions and universities, researchers reveal that varying degrees of support are provided to assist with knowledge exchange. When asked about if the research institutions or universities of participants provide specific strategies that guide their approach to knowledge exchange with potential research users, a broad range of replies were received. As *Figure 5.1* illustrates, over one third of participants either agree (27.6%) or strongly agree (7%) that they are supported with strategies. However, relatively comparable proportions of participants neither agree or disagree (19.8%), disagree (17.9%) or strongly disagree (6.2%) to the same statement. These findings suggest that there are significant disparities between the guidance that is provided to researchers by their employers. Indeed, similarly varied responses are recorded when researchers discuss the level to which their institution or university deliver incentives to exchange knowledge with research users. *Figure 28* demonstrates how around one third of participants either agree (24.9%) or strongly agree (6%) that the necessary incentives to engage with potential users are provided by their employer. On the other hand, high numbers of researchers neither agree nor disagree (20.1%), disagree (19.7%) or strongly disagree (7.8%) when responding to the same question. This suggests that many researchers are self-motivated to engage with users of their research and are not necessarily guided or encouraged by their employer.

Figure 28: Institutional strategies for knowledge exchange

Figure 29: Institutional incentives for knowledge exchange

MISTRAL-ITN Knowledge Exchange Survey

When responding to a question that asked how the institutions or universities of researchers promoted engagement with knowledge exchange, a broad range of aspects were recorded. One third of participants (33%) suggested that their institution or university promoted direct interaction with relevant users, whilst similar amounts of researchers (29.4%) asserted that their employers commit resources that help promote knowledge exchange. Lower numbers of participants felt that their institution or university maintains a comprehensive list of potential research users (12.9%) or that they use other organisations as intermediaries to engage with research users (19.1%). This information is presented in *Figure 30*. When provided with the opportunity to provide further insight to their response, researchers discuss how their institutions and universities “encourage internships and research engagement with academic institutions” (12206852558) and “encourage us to seek international partnerships” (12127100607). One researcher mentioned that they have received “fund to create a research-based podcast” (12223197473), whilst another stated that their institution “have a unit available for transfer of research into society” (12128644969). Moreover, a researcher discussed how they have “specific champions in the workplace who have formed successful relationships and engagement lead teams to help others” (12148359982).

Figure 30: Institutional promotion of knowledge exchange

Despite an array of good examples of support and guidance for knowledge exchange mentioned by researchers, a much greater number issues and concerns are raised by participants. Indeed, one researcher clarified how “a lot of statements of good intentions are put out there but there is a lack of meaningful resources - therefore my team built its own knowledge exchange network” (12126126164). This sentiment was furthered by another respondent who argued that “engagement is encouraged in a general sense, but no specific help / incentives / strategies exist for my research field (energy transition)” (12129123367). Whilst some participants note that their university simply “doesn't promote engagement” (12125684193), others note how “as far as I know, there is nothing procedural. It is left to the device of researchers” (12212485131). These responses highlight how many researchers feel that they must instigate knowledge exchange approaches on their own accord and that they are not sufficiently supported or guided by their employers in this regard.

When self-reflecting on their research experiences, the survey findings reveal a number of trends amongst researchers. There is confidence between participants that, when they have completed a specific piece of research, it is often (49%) or always (15.5%) trusted by research users in terms of its quality. Less confidence is noted when considering how research is evaluated by potential users for how effective participants' work is in achieving knowledge exchange. Around a third of participants (29.5%) feel that this style of evaluation never occurs, while a further 44.2% suggest that it only happens sometimes. A mixed response is revealed in regard

MISTRAL-ITN Knowledge Exchange Survey

to the degree to which researchers self-reflect on whether their knowledge exchanges approaches could be improved. Around half of participants (46.6%) suggest that they only sometimes conduct self-reflection in this manner, whilst one third (32.4%) often do so and a further 13% always do. These findings are revealed in *Figure 31*. When reflecting on their priorities moving forward, participants show broad agreement in regard to how they will do things differently. *Figure 32* illustrates how high proportions of researchers acknowledge the importance of engaging in dialogue with potential users of their research in relation to how they can best meet and develop their needs. Over one third of participants (37.5%) assert that they will do so often, whilst a further 14.4% state that they will so always. Similar proportions of participants suggest that they ensure investment in future impact is informed by past experience. Almost half of participants (43%) assert that they will often ensure that learning on knowledge exchange is applied to their future research projects, with a further 21.4% suggesting that they will always do so.

Figure 31: Knowledge exchange actions on completion of research projects

Figure 32: Future priorities for knowledge exchange

MISTRAL-ITN Knowledge Exchange Survey

A final issue revealed in this theme regards the perceptions of researchers in relation to the potential impact of the COVID-19 pandemic (Figure 33). There was an almost even split between participants, with 53.1% suggesting that their approach to knowledge exchange will not change as a consequence of COVID and 46.9% arguing that it will. In open responses, multiple researchers mentioned the shift to online forms of exchange that the pandemic has led to and had varying perceptions of the benefits of this. Participants stated that, "it has changed the traditional knowledge exchange to virtual or more digital" (12126510076) and that "almost all my research will be shifted online. This means more webinars for knowledge exchange, learning how to archive talks/events and material on university and other sites, more op-eds, policy briefs and blog posts" (12171394517). Discussing the benefits of a more digital approach, one respondent noted how "after using Zoom and other communication methods, I feel it becomes more easy to contact with many researchers and I could have more opportunity to attend on-line international conferences" (12126241889). An online approach also represented a benefit to some researchers in the sense that it results in "absolutely less travel" (12130347919). However, there are also multiple negative perceptions of the impact of COVID-19 on research and knowledge exchange processes, with participants concerned by "fewer face-to-face exchanges (& this is, in my experience, is the best way to communicate research findings)" (12128422499) and an acknowledgment that "it [COVID-19] restricts the reach to those that could benefit from the research results" (12136081201). These comments reflect the divergent opinions of researchers regarding the manner in which the pandemic will impact upon their research activities.

Figure 33: Post-pandemic approaches to knowledge exchange

There is also evidence that many researchers are worried that the pandemic will negatively impact upon the capacity of research to adequately engage with societal needs. This suggests that new ideas and concepts for conducting research may need to be created to deal with emerging issues. Participants mentioned that COVID-19 will reveal "a greater consideration of the social issues and current needs that exist. The challenge is finding effective methods to knowledge exchange in this regard" (12126684683). Others asserted that the pandemic has "generated more challenges and highlighted important social problems that force us as academics to reflect and react more with new and innovative mechanisms" (12206641238). These concerns were furthered by a researcher who argued that "COVID-19 is going to affect everything. One of my worries is that inequality, poverty, and social exclusion are going to increase and I feel that I should focus more on these issues and on particular groups of the population" (12125441328). In this sense, the pandemic may force researchers to change their approach to research and may lead to the establishment of new relationship between researchers and

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie actions grant agreement MISTRAL No 813837

MISTRAL-ITN Knowledge Exchange Survey

research subjects. Indeed, some participants mentioned how they already have "*better involvement with social media*" (12207293197) as a tool for knowledge exchange. Other suggested that, "*in a new world of remote communication there may actually be increased opportunities to conduct more knowledge exchange through the increasing prominence of online events. E.g., being able to attend a conference without actually attending*" (12133505439). Participants were keen to highlight how the shift to online engagement raises important ethical and administrative issues that can be challenging to efficiently respond to. As one researcher argued, "*bureaucracy has dramatically increased, thus preventing us for doing the real job*" (12225326141). In general, the pandemic will (and already has) had a significant impact upon the work of researchers. Even as restrictions have lessened and the ability to engage in face-to-face settings has returned, many impacts of the pandemic remain. Central to these, is the shift to digitalisation. As researchers highlight, this brings both opportunities and challenges for knowledge exchange. The most pressing challenges appear to revolve around the diminished capacity of research to critically engage and tackle social issues.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie actions grant agreement MISTRAL No 813837

MISTRAL-ITN Knowledge Exchange Survey

6. Key findings and conclusions

This report has presented the findings of a knowledge exchange survey focusing on social science researchers working on sustainability issues. Clear trends amongst the perceptions and opinions of researchers are revealed, yet there is also evidence of divergence between participants. Similarly, multiple concerns regarding current knowledge exchange approaches are revealed. These include reservations about the time and capacity that some researchers have to engage such activities, as well as the varying degrees of support and guidance that is (or often is not) provided by the institutions and universities of researchers. These concerns are matched by an array of opportunities that are put forward by some participants, with many researchers revealing insightful recommendations on how they believe knowledge exchange processes can become more effective and efficient. An increased digital approach to knowledge exchange, brought on by the COVID-19 pandemic, has been received with mixed views from researchers. Whilst the potential to conduct research without the requirement of travel is viewed as a benefit for many, the lack of face-to-face engagement is deemed as a significant limitation to knowledge exchange approaches. There are also concerns regarding the capacity of a more online focused approach to research being capable of tackling the major societal problems that exist. As a means of concluding this report, the major findings are listed below in bullet points:

- Two thirds of participants (62.3%) work on research with teaching responsibilities.
- Over half of participants (53.5%) have more than 10 years of research experience.
- More participants conduct their research where their organisation is located (69.4%) than internationally (30.6%).
- Although not by a significant majority, more participants feel that academic research has the greatest impact if researchers strive to be advocates of particular issues (49.5%) than by being objective honest brokers of knowledge (36.9%).
- Participants are split in relation to their methods of engagement with potential users of their research, with 36.7% doing so on an issue-by-issue basis and 38.7% aiming to foster long-term relationships.
- High proportions of participants feel that they have a good understanding of the research needs of key research users, with experience of communicating research findings to a wide range of audiences being seen as a key factor.
- Smaller proportions of participants feel that key stakeholders and research users have a good understanding of their research strengths, whilst only slightly over a third of participants assert that they regularly meet with key users to extend cooperation and develop mutual capacities.
- Non-academic channels of communication (including social media) are becoming key pathways to research impact amongst non-academic audiences.
- The vast majority of participants agree that potential research impact through evidence-based decision making is an important consideration.
- Although papers for peer reviewed journals are prioritized above other forms of output, there are concerns that this is a time-consuming and exclusive approach to disseminating findings.
- Over one third of participants ensure that research users are able to participate in the design of their research, yet ethical and political reasons are revealed as restricting factors in this regard.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie actions grant agreement MISTRAL No 813837

MISTRAL-ITN Knowledge Exchange Survey

- More researchers publish their work in subscription journals than in open access journals, mainly due to financial constraints.
- Around half of participants note that their research institutions/universities provide specific strategies that guide their knowledge exchange approaches, yet comparatively similar proportions argue that they are 'left to their own devices' in this regard.
- Participants are confident that their research is trusted by research users in terms of its quality.
- There is little evidence of research users evaluating the work of researchers in regard to how it has resulted in impact or how it could more effectively be exchanged.
- Learning and self-reflection on previous knowledge exchange experiences is acknowledged as a key factor for a majority of participants.
- Engaging in dialogue with potential research users about how best to meet and develop research needs is also recognised as an important factor going forward.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie actions grant agreement MISTRAL No 813837

MISTRAL-ITN Knowledge Exchange Survey

Appendix: Search criteria for identifying participants in the MISTRAL Knowledge exchange Survey

We used the Scopus database to define our population to any article or review within the 'social sciences' subject area (as classified by Scopus) with 'energy' in the abstract, title or keywords, published between 2016 and 2020 (inclusive, a five-year period). We excluded subject areas not of interest (as many documents are classified in more than one subject area). From this we manually excluded source titles (mostly journals) that do clearly not publish in the domain of interest (judging by their title), after which we limited our search to the 30 most active sources (judged by number of outputs). This search gave 7,060 document results. In order to ensure that we did not miss outputs from any key journals that may not be classified by Scopus as expected, we performed a second search. Here we used the generic keywords 'energy' and the wildcard 'soci*' to find articles or reviews in the same five-year period. We excluded subject areas that were clearly irrelevant and ended with 4,872 results.

We combined the results from the above two searches and the corresponding author field was used to access email addresses. All duplicates (researchers who were corresponding author for more than one result in our final search) and empty results (that had no email listed for corresponding) were deleted. A final list of 10,249 unique authors / email addresses remained.

Search 1:

```
TITLE-ABS-KEY(energy) AND ( LIMIT-TO ( SUBJAREA,"SOCI" ) OR EXCLUDE ( SUBJAREA,"ENGI" ) OR EXCLUDE ( SUBJAREA,"COMP" ) OR EXCLUDE ( SUBJAREA,"MATH" ) OR EXCLUDE ( SUBJAREA,"MEDI" ) OR EXCLUDE ( SUBJAREA,"AGRI" ) ) AND ( LIMIT-TO ( DOCTYPE,"ar" ) OR LIMIT-TO ( DOCTYPE,"re" ) ) AND ( LIMIT-TO ( PUBYEAR,2020) OR LIMIT-TO ( PUBYEAR,2019) OR LIMIT-TO ( PUBYEAR,2018) OR LIMIT-TO ( PUBYEAR,2017) OR LIMIT-TO ( PUBYEAR,2016) ) AND ( LIMIT-TO ( EXACTSRCTITLE,"Sustainability Switzerland" ) OR LIMIT-TO ( EXACTSRCTITLE,"Building And Environment" ) OR LIMIT-TO ( EXACTSRCTITLE,"Energy Research And Social Science" ) OR LIMIT-TO ( EXACTSRCTITLE,"Sustainable Cities And Society" ) OR LIMIT-TO ( EXACTSRCTITLE,"Energy For Sustainable Development" ) OR LIMIT-TO ( EXACTSRCTITLE,"Advanced Science Letters" ) OR LIMIT-TO ( EXACTSRCTITLE,"International Journal Of Scientific And Technology Research" ) OR LIMIT-TO ( EXACTSRCTITLE,"Transportation Research Part D Transport And Environment" ) OR LIMIT-TO ( EXACTSRCTITLE,"Journal Of Industrial Ecology" ) OR LIMIT-TO ( EXACTSRCTITLE,"Utilities Policy" ) OR LIMIT-TO ( EXACTSRCTITLE,"Energy Sustainability And Society" ) OR LIMIT-TO ( EXACTSRCTITLE,"Environment Development And Sustainability" ) OR LIMIT-TO ( EXACTSRCTITLE,"Environmental Science And Policy" ) OR LIMIT-TO ( EXACTSRCTITLE,"Journal Of Green Building" ) OR LIMIT-TO ( EXACTSRCTITLE,"Resources Policy" ) OR LIMIT-TO ( EXACTSRCTITLE,"Nature Climate Change" ) OR LIMIT-TO ( EXACTSRCTITLE,"International Journal Of Sustainable Energy Planning And Management" ) OR LIMIT-TO ( EXACTSRCTITLE,"Land Use Policy" ) OR LIMIT-TO ( EXACTSRCTITLE,"Global Environmental Change" ) OR LIMIT-TO ( EXACTSRCTITLE,"Environmental Innovation And Societal Transitions" ) OR LIMIT-TO ( EXACTSRCTITLE,"Marine Policy" ) OR LIMIT-TO ( EXACTSRCTITLE,"International Journal Of Energy Technology And Policy" ) OR LIMIT-TO ( EXACTSRCTITLE,"International Journal Of Sustainable Development And Planning" ) OR LIMIT-TO ( EXACTSRCTITLE,"Environmental Impact Assessment Review" ) OR LIMIT-TO ( EXACTSRCTITLE,"Sustainability" ) OR LIMIT-TO ( EXACTSRCTITLE,"Local Environment" ) OR LIMIT-TO ( EXACTSRCTITLE,"Current Opinion In Environmental Sustainability" ) OR LIMIT-TO ( EXACTSRCTITLE,"American Journal Of Physical Anthropology" ) OR LIMIT-TO ( EXACTSRCTITLE,"Environmental Politics" ) OR LIMIT-TO ( EXACTSRCTITLE,"International Journal Of
```


This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie actions grant agreement MISTRAL No 813837

MISTRAL-ITN Knowledge Exchange Survey

Energy Production And Management") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTSRCTITLE,"Journal Of Chemical Information And Modeling") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTSRCTITLE,"Water Switzerland") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTSRCTITLE,"Journal Of Fluorescence") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTSRCTITLE,"Safety Science") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTSRCTITLE,"Journal Of Chemical Education") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTSRCTITLE,"International Journal Of Crashworthiness") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTSRCTITLE,"Journal Of Information And Computational Science") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTSRCTITLE,"IEEE Transactions On Transportation Electrification") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTSRCTITLE,"Zhongguo Gonglu Xuebao China Journal Of Highway And Transport") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTSRCTITLE,"Journal Of Water Resources Planning And Management") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTSRCTITLE,"Transportation Research Part C Emerging Technologies") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTSRCTITLE,"Earth Surface Processes And Landforms") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTSRCTITLE,"Bulletin Of The Atomic Scientists") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTSRCTITLE,"Teoriya I Praktika Fizicheskoy Kultury") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTSRCTITLE,"Physics Education") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTSRCTITLE,"Urban Climate") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTSRCTITLE,"Transportation Research Part A Policy And Practice") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTSRCTITLE,"American Journal Of Human Biology") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTSRCTITLE,"Journal Of Asian Architecture And Building Engineering") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTSRCTITLE,"Physics Teacher") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTSRCTITLE,"Revista Brasileira De Ensino De Fisica") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTSRCTITLE,"IEEE Transactions On Information Theory") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTSRCTITLE,"Economic And Political Weekly") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTSRCTITLE,"Journal Of Archaeological Science Reports") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTSRCTITLE,"Food And Nutrition Bulletin") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTSRCTITLE,"Foods") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTSRCTITLE,"Quaternary Science Reviews") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTSRCTITLE,"Journal Of Mountain Science") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTSRCTITLE,"Dili Xuebao Acta Geographica Sinica") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTSRCTITLE,"Jiaotong Yunshu Xitong Gongcheng Yu Xinxi Journal Of Transportation Systems Engineering And Information Technology") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTSRCTITLE,"Journal Of Archaeological Science") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTSRCTITLE,"Obesity Facts") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTSRCTITLE,"Federal Register") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTSRCTITLE,"Forest Policy And Economics") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTSRCTITLE,"Archives Of Gerontology And Geriatrics") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTSRCTITLE,"Journal Of Applied Engineering Science") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTSRCTITLE,"Economy Of Region") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTSRCTITLE,"Facilities") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTSRCTITLE,"Archaeometry") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTSRCTITLE,"Heritage Science") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTSRCTITLE,"ISPRS International Journal Of Geo Information") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTSRCTITLE,"Periodico Tche Quimica") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTSRCTITLE,"Iet Intelligent Transport Systems") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTSRCTITLE,"International Journal Of Speech Technology") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTSRCTITLE,"Scientometrics") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTSRCTITLE,"Yaogan Xuebao Journal Of Remote Sensing") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTSRCTITLE,"Extractive Industries And Society") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTSRCTITLE,"Food Analytical Methods") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTSRCTITLE,"Applied Ergonomics") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTSRCTITLE,"Archaeological And Anthropological Sciences") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTSRCTITLE,"International Journal Of Electrical Engineering Education") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTSRCTITLE,"International Journal Of Sustainability In Higher Education") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTSRCTITLE,"Disaster Advances") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTSRCTITLE,"Food Policy") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTSRCTITLE,"Geriatrics And Gerontology International") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTSRCTITLE,"Habitat International") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTSRCTITLE,"Open House International") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTSRCTITLE,"Journal Of Information Science And Engineering") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTSRCTITLE,"Economic Annals Xxi") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTSRCTITLE,"Futuribles Analyse Et Prospective") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTSRCTITLE,"International Journal Of Water Resources Development") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTSRCTITLE,"Progress In Industrial Ecology") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTSRCTITLE,"Resonance") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTSRCTITLE,"Wseas Transactions On Power Systems")

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie actions grant agreement MISTRAL No 813837

MISTRAL-ITN Knowledge Exchange Survey

OR EXCLUDE (EXACTSRCTITLE,"Ergonomics") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTSRCTITLE,"Problemy Ekorozwoju")
OR EXCLUDE (EXACTSRCTITLE,"Speech Communication") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTSRCTITLE,"South African
Journal Of Chemical Engineering") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTSRCTITLE,"Frontiers Of Architectural Research")
OR EXCLUDE (EXACTSRCTITLE,"Transportation Research Part B Methodological") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTSRCTITLE,"Concurrences") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTSRCTITLE,"Journal Of Security And Sustainability Issues") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTSRCTITLE,"American Journal Of Health Promotion") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTSRCTITLE,"Process Integration And Optimization For Sustainability") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTSRCTITLE,"Anuario Do Instituto De Geociencias") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTSRCTITLE,"Journal Of Human Evolution") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTSRCTITLE,"Scientific Data") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTSRCTITLE,"Social Science And Medicine") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTSRCTITLE,"Strategic Analysis") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTSRCTITLE,"Computer Standards And Interfaces") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTSRCTITLE,"Rivista Di Studi Sulla Sostenibilita") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTSRCTITLE,"Urban Water Journal"))

Search 2:

(KEY (energy) AND KEY (soci*)) AND DOCTYPE (ar OR re) AND PUBYEAR > 2015 AND PUBYEAR < 2021 AND NOT SUBJAREA (soci) AND (EXCLUDE (SUBJAREA , "MEDI") OR EXCLUDE (SUBJAREA , "COMP") OR EXCLUDE (SUBJAREA , "MATE") OR EXCLUDE (SUBJAREA , "MATH") OR EXCLUDE (SUBJAREA , "BIOC") OR EXCLUDE (SUBJAREA , "CHEM") OR EXCLUDE (SUBJAREA , "CENG") OR EXCLUDE (SUBJAREA , "PHYS") OR EXCLUDE (SUBJAREA , "NEUR") OR EXCLUDE (SUBJAREA , "DECI") OR EXCLUDE (SUBJAREA , "PHAR") OR EXCLUDE (SUBJAREA , "IMMU") OR EXCLUDE (SUBJAREA , "VETE") OR EXCLUDE (SUBJAREA , "DENT") OR EXCLUDE (SUBJAREA , "NURS"))